

QUICK PHOTOGRAPHIC KEY TO THE *SYNEMA* FROM SOUTH AFRICA

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Synema decens (Karsch, 1878)

Synema diana (Audouin, 1826)

Synema imitatrix (Pavesi, 1883)

Synema langheldi Dahl, 1907

Synema mandibulare Dahl, 1907

Synema marlothi Dahl, 1907

***Synema nigrotibiale* Lessert, 1919**

***Synema riflense* Strand, 1909**

***Synema simoneae* Lessert, 191**

***Synema vallotoni* Lessert, 1923**

For more information and credits for photographs used see

Dippenaar-Schoeman A.S., Haddad C.R., Foord S.H., & Lotz L.N. (2020) *The Thomisidae of South Africa*. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide: The Thomisidae of South Africa (S-T) Part 3, Version 1: 1-79. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7513278>